

The **first** trans-continental **Networking Academy** for **African and European Digital Innovation Hubs.**

D5.1 The AfriConEU Community Report (Interim)

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Glossary and Abbreviations

DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
MS	Milestone

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Executive Summary

The AfriConEU community interim report intends to (1) document all the activities that were carried out so far to encourage AfriConEU community members' engagement, (2) present the respective results achieved in terms of interaction and value created and (3) provide an overview on the Talent Matchmaking activities and outcomes.

This deliverable will be structured as follows: first, the AfriConEU Community of Practice and its goals will be presented as well as the strategies that the consortium adopted to build and grow the community. Then, the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) of the AfriConEU Community and their evolution during the first year of the project activity will be presented. This is possible through the use of a control internal tool named AfriConEU Monitoring File that was created to keep track of the main value indicators of the community. Finally, a closing section with some next steps and strategies foreseen to uptake the community and walk towards the ambitious KPIs will be presented.

Moreover, this report will be revised by M35, where a final version will provide updated information on the activities carried out to engage members and present the final results achieved in terms of interaction and value created.

1. The AfriConEU Community

The AfriConEU project aims at presenting a solution that enhances the capacity of the African DIHs to accelerate the digital transformation of the African economy and society. This will be achieved through a tailor-made designed mechanism named **AfriConEU Networking Academy** that, as illustrated in Figure 1, will offer 2 Flagship Programmes: **1) DIHs Capacity Building** and **2) Trans-continental Partnership Development**.

In addition, and to further support the Academy, a multi-actor knowledge-sharing Community of Practice - **The AfriConEU Community** – has also become a crucial part of the solution. Officially established by M6 (July 2021), the AfriConEU Community establishment started with a discussion on its meaning: initially thought to be *AfriConEU Online Community*, the project partners agreed that this wording could mislead people to think that the community would be run in an online platform where individuals and/or entities would register and have its own profile on the AfriConEU website. This is not the case. As such, AfriConEU consortium agreed to re-name the community to *AfriConEU Community of Practice*, as this reflects better the intentions of the project and the level of involvement pursued for the community members, who are stimulated to take part in the different project activities (both online and on-site) and actively contribute to them.

The AfriConEU Community of Practice is now fully operational. The project’s website¹ and social media channels are the key touchpoints for the community members, and any relevant stakeholder (DIHs, entrepreneurs, ecosystem builders, accelerators, mentors, startups, investors, corporates, members of the African Diaspora Community etc.) from different regions in Africa and Europe can be part of it.

Figure 1 - The AfriConEU Networking Academy

¹ <https://www.africoneu.eu/africoneu-community-of-practice/>

All AfriConEU partners contribute to the engagement and animation of the community. INOVA+ (AfriConEU project coordinator) is the designated community moderator and therefore responsible partner for designing and coordinating the processes that have been followed for the community set up and management and for achieving the foreseen outcomes.

The community objectives and foreseen engagement strategies, target groups and tools/channels used for its operationalization are detailed in the following sub-sections.

1.1. Goals

One of the specific objectives of the AfriConEU project is to:

“Engage African and European DIHs, entrepreneurs, investors, and policymakers in a community of networked ecosystems that will foster the sustainability of the project results and the exploitation of opportunities between the two continents.”

To achieve this goal, several **sub-objectives** are set to be met, as follows:

Facilitate dialogue, experience sharing and collaboration between stakeholders from both continents.

Help DIHs to identify complementarities, synergies and potential collaborations leading to a better service offering to their regional/local companies and Startups.

Enable sharing of best practices and experiences towards addressing challenges faced by DIHs.

Enable co-design of strategies, tools and resources for technology evolution to cope with future and upcoming needs.

Ease innovation transfer overcoming national frontiers.

Connect stakeholders from the innovation ecosystems.

The AfriConEU integrates a “talent matchmaking” feature to connect African and European Startups looking for skilled talents.

To respond to these challenges in the best possible way, the project has established a **Community of Practice** that has been continuously animated and nurtured throughout the project duration, enforcing exchange and mutually beneficial cooperation between Africa and Europe.

1.2. Development and Engagement Strategies

Developing a robust ecosystem for a community like the one AfriConEU is establishing is a big challenge, from its creation to its support and upkeep. AfriConEU consortium has designed several strategies to address successfully this challenge and cover efficiently all the objectives listed in the previous sub-section.

1.2.1. Project Activities

Although the AfriConEU multi-actor knowledge-sharing community set-up and operation kicked off officially only by M6 (Task 5.1), the strategy for attracting interested stakeholders in the project’s activities started being developed since the beginning of the project as part of the dissemination and communication plan that YMH developed within WP6. The strategies outlined in the respective report (D6.1) to raise awareness of the project and promote its activities and results, also contribute directly to the AfriConEU community of practice development. These include not only the communication and promotion materials disseminated through the website and social media channels but also the partners' efforts in engaging their local and personnel networks to connect with the project.

Figure 2 - Section “What's New” in the AfriConEU Website

Moreover, all the participants invited speakers and moderators of the AfriConEU roundtables and workshops, and the respondents of the conducted surveys were the first groups to be part of the AfriConEU Community of Practice (especially the ones that took part in the designed and organised activities within WP2 and that respect to Phase 1 of the project - *Context and state of the art analysis*).

1.2.2. The ICT-58 Projects

In addition to the stakeholders that have been directly involved in the activities mentioned in the previous point, the AfriConEU consortium also seeks collaborations and potential synergies with other relevant individuals, organisations and projects to further expand the potential of the AU-EU digital cooperation alliance. In this sense, and aligned with the objectives of T1.5 of the project, the AfriConEU consortium reached out to the other ICT-58 funded projects in order to establish a close collaboration with them through an enforced, diversified and coordinated effort to create a common digital innovation ecosystem between the two continents.

INOVA+, the project coordinator and responsible partner for ensuring AfriConEU works closely with the rest of the ICT-58 funded projects (T1.5), started the so-called “*ICT-58 Family meetings*” in June 2021 (M5) with the aim of: (1) presenting each of the projects and sharing their progress and findings so far; (2) identify common challenges and learn from each other to improve; (3) align communication strategies and discuss joint efforts for reaching a larger audience and enhancing the project's impact; and (4) participate in each other's events and activities.

At the moment, two *ICT-58 family meetings* took place and a third one will occur in March 2022 (M14). The first meetings were attended by AfriConEU, [DIGILOGIC](#) and [HUBiquitous](#) projects. The third meeting will have the participation of the recent projects approved under the ICT-58 topic, namely [D4DHub](#) and [AEDIB|NET](#), who were also invited to start participating in these discussions and therefore, to be part of the community.

Figure 3 - ICT-58 Family Meeting post on social media (left); Printscren of an ICT-58 Family Meeting (right)

1.2.3. Target Groups

The Community of Practice is composed of individuals and entities of the AfriConEU target groups (DIHs, entrepreneurs, investors, startups, SMEs, innovation stakeholders, etc. from Europe and Africa) to whom all the activities and communication and dissemination actions of the project are aimed. Beyond the unilateral communication channels used where AfriConEU as a project initiates the interaction with its target audience, the consortium also wanted to broaden the meaning of this exchange and make it bilateral. In this respect, two extra pages were created in the AfriConEU website under the tab *Join: For Individuals* and *For Entities* (as you can see in the figure below).

The goal is to have a place within the AfriConEU channels where the project's public can interact with the consortium and inform them about what type of opportunities they are looking for:

- **For Individuals:** For entrepreneurs, stakeholders, policymakers, investors, etc. they can fill in a [form](#)² (See Annex I) and express to what opportunities they would like to have access to (Training Seminars, Online Courses, Webinars, Funding, Job Openings and/or conferences);
- **For Entities:** For related organisations, they can fill in a [form](#)³ (See Annex II) and share what type of opportunities (from training seminars, online courses, webinars, funding, job openings, conferences, etc.) they can offer to the AfriConEU Online Community.

Through this mechanism, the AfriConEU team will be able to not only share content that interests its followers but also redirect its social media communication to specific targets, making sure the expressed requests will be fulfilled. Furthermore, they will be included in the project's database to be reached out to every time AfriConEU has some match to their needs.

1.2.4. Dissemination and Communication efforts and participation in relevant activities and events

On the AfriConEU website, a repository of upcoming opportunities, including events, conferences, training seminars, and webinars relevant for digital innovation hubs, entrepreneurs, tech-hubs and startups in both Africa and Europe is available for anyone to

² <https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSckobWP9oNsRjy3k3tCO1TdPa7JWxAraf8kxgm6l82wLwL2KQ/viewform>

³ https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSdJILShieEACmfY_GlVtIttyAruj29ajxDhMZJIDwjCBf0MoWQ/viewform

consult (see website page [Events](#)⁴). Combined with an effective and constant communication of these events in the social media channels, this strategy guarantees that the community is regularly informed with up-to-date information regarding the trending digital events in Europe and Africa.

AfriConEU's partners themselves participate in some of these events and publish them on their social media, promoting the project and its main message and goals within their networks. On the website page [Participation in Events](#)⁵, the AfriConEU presentations on some important events (like the ones from *Africa Europe Innovation Partnership* and *Big Impact Days*) are available for the whole community.

Lastly, partners are making continuous efforts to disseminate the project's press releases at their national level and among their networks together with the attention of the target audiences. At the same time, the partners in charge of the organization of the AfriConEU activities are encouraging participants to subscribe to the newsletter to keep up with the community developments.

Figure 4 - Section Events of the AfriConEU website

1.2.5. Talent Matchmaking

One of the AfriConEU aims is to contribute to job creation by fostering innovation and entrepreneurship of African economies. The project will achieve this not only through the

⁴ <https://www.africoneu.eu/events/>

⁵ <https://www.africoneu.eu/participation-in-events/>

AfriConEU Academy programmes, but also through the project’s Community of Practice environment by developing a “talent matchmaking” feature⁶ to support local youth employment and help startups to meet their needs for digital skilled staff.

All project partners have been attentive and reported relevant job offers they come across in their networks and informed the communication and dissemination responsible partner (YMH) about them. In its turn, these job offers are being reposted on the project’s website to encourage the members of the community to find and hire talents from Africa, and promoted on the social media (Figure 5). The forms (for individuals and entities) mentioned in the previous subsection 1.2.3. will also be used for this purpose at a later stage.

Figure 5 - Job Opportunities' posts on the AfriConEU’s social media

⁶ <https://www.africoneu.eu/job-opportunities/>

2. Understand the community value – Key performance indicators

As already stated in Section 1, to ensure the long-term sustainability of the project results as well as the exploitation of the still untapped opportunities that exist between the two continents, the project is creating a Trans-Continental Community of stakeholders (namely the AfriConEU Community of Practice) that will enforce exchange and mutually beneficial cooperation between Africa and Europe. To achieve this goal the following sub-objectives are set:

- Develop the AfriConEU Community comprised of multiple actors such as DIHs, start-ups, investors, Africa diaspora members etc. from both continents and facilitate online interactions, exchange and long-term engagement even after the end of the project;
- Integrate a Talent Matchmaking feature into the AfriConEU online channels to connect African and European startups looking for skilled talents.

These objectives need to have associated Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that are achievable and measurable so that the consortium can understand the community value that is being created and will endure over the project's completion.

Overall, all feeds, applications, exchanges and information will be tractable and transformed into indicators (see table below) that enable a better understanding of the community value to the DIHs, and its evolution over time.

Table 1 - AfriConEU Community of Practice KPIs

Number of stakeholders reached through the AfriconEU Community of Practice	>3000
Connections made for exchange of knowledge through the AfriConEU Community of Practice	>200
Number of synergies with relevant trans-continental and inter-continental networks, projects and initiatives	>40

In order to keep track of these indicators, an internal monitoring tool was created so that all partners could contribute with relevant data coming from their activities and interactions. The next section further details this instrument's aim and structure.

2.1. The AfriConEU community monitoring file

In order to keep track and collect all relevant information to not only understand the community value but also to monitor the KPIs associated with the AfriConEU Community of Practice, a monitoring file was developed so that AfriConEU partners can register all relevant data that comes from their activities and/or dissemination efforts. This is intended to be a living document, always up to date, that shall be used until the end of the project to collect information that will be reflected in the community report's final version, by M35.

The **AfriConEU community monitoring file** was designed in an excel format containing 5 different sheets, as follows:

- **Guide:** the first sheet of the document contains a detailed guide for the AfriConEU partners to know how to fill in the engagement monitoring file;
- **Stakeholders:** Lists all stakeholders reached through the AfriconEU Community of Practice. All stakeholders involved in AfriConEU events/activities (roundtables, interviews, events, bootcamps, etc.) and in the community should be listed in this sheet (along with their respective information).
- **Connections:** List of connections made for the exchange of knowledge through the AfriConEU Community of Practice. All stakeholders involved in AfriConEU events/activities (roundtables, interviews, events, bootcamps, etc.) that are related to the exchange of knowledge should be listed in this sheet (along with their respective information).
- **Synergies:** Lists the synergies created with relevant trans-continental and inter-continental networks, projects and initiatives. Project Partners should add to this list all the projects, initiatives or networks that are connected to AfriConEU in some way.
- **Talent Matchmaking:** Lists all the job and training offers disseminated via the AfriConEU's channels. YMH is the main responsible partner to keep this section up to date however, if any other partner is aware of some job offer that can or was disseminated among the AfriConEU's community should also fill in this sheet.

In **Annex III**, the template of the AfriConEU community monitoring file is presented, as well as a detailed explanation of what is requested in each one of the sheets (see Guide sheet screenshot).

The premise is that each partner is not only responsible to fill in the document with information concerning their leading activities/events but also should be proactive and identify relevant data to be disseminated within the project networks (training/job offers, events, etc.) or existing initiatives/projects deemed relevant to create synergies with AfriConEU.

2.2. Evolution of the Key Performance Indicators (by M13) and MS6 achievement

As presented in section 2, the AfriConEU community aims to attain ambitious KPIs during its lifespan. The next sub-sections explain the project performance towards these KPIs:

2.2.1. Number of stakeholders reached through the AfriconEU Community of Practice

During the first 13 months of the project, the AfriConEU was able to reach a variety of stakeholders through its activities, namely: the 4 roundtables hosted within T2.1 to set the scene in the African ecosystems; the surveys that were distributed to DIH's and DIH helpers and the interviews conducted to gather feedback and lessons learned from existing initiatives and discover good practices within T2.2; the 4 roundtables hosted within T2.3 to identify the current perceptions towards cross-continental and intracontinental partnerships and define particular needs and preferences; and the international participative workshop that took place on 3 February 2022 as part of the WP3 objective to design the 2 flagship programmes. The stakeholders took part in the activities as participants (attendees, interviewees, survey respondents), invited speakers or moderators.

Based on the Community Monitoring File, **617 stakeholders** were reached through the AfriConEU activities by M13, which makes **MS6 – AfriConEU Community with 500 members also achieved by its due date (M13)**.

Figures 6, 7, 8 and 9 reveal more details on the AfriConEU Community. As it can be analysed, the AfriConEU community of Practice within the first year is composed of more male stakeholders than females (29% vs 13%); the majority of the community is from the African continent (80%); the type of organisation more represented are DIHs (64%), followed by start-ups (14%); and the great majority are participants in the project conducted activities so far.

Also, it is interesting to note that many of these stakeholders are participants in more than one AfriConEU event/activity which is a good indicator for the project's results sustainable uptake.

Figure 6 - Gender of the AfriConEU Community of Practice stakeholders

Figure 7 - Type of Involvement of the AfriConEU Community stakeholders

Figure 8 - Type of Organisation of the AfriConEU Community stakeholders

Figure 9 - Nationality of the AfriConEU Community stakeholders

2.2.2. Connections made for the exchange of knowledge through the AfriConEU Community of Practice

This KPI aims to count the number of connections between different stakeholders (DIHs with DIHs, startups with investors; startups with coaches; startups with DIHs, etc.) encouraged by the AfriConEU consortium. The first year of the project focused mainly on *Phase 1 – Context and state of the art analysis* and at the start of *Phase 2- Development of the AFriConEU Networking Academy*. In this context, the events and activities performed were more research-oriented, aiming at getting as much information as possible from the relevant stakeholders, their current needs and challenges and how to respond to them in the most appropriate way possible.

In this sense, this KPI will become trackable when the 2 Academy flagship programmes kick-off, as more specific actions towards the engagement and connection of the community members will be designed and enforced (in addition to the already planned activities with this aim such as the International Brokerage event expected to be hosted during the Implementation phase).

The forms available on the website for both individuals and entities (*section 1.2.3*) will also be used to encourage these connections as soon as more responses are received.

2.2.3. Number of synergies with relevant trans-continental and inter-continental networks, projects and initiatives

Within the first year of project, the AfriConEU project made multiple efforts to engage in synergies with relevant trans-continental and intercontinental networks, projects and initiatives, starting with the projects funded within the same HORIZON 2020 call, the ICT-58 projects⁷.

Furthermore, the project also associated and reached well-known networks and initiatives in the field, such as the [Africa Europe Innovation Partnership](#)⁸ where AfriConEU participated in 2 of their events in 2021. Other initiatives such as [AfriLabs](#) and [Emerging Valley](#) are also events that the AfriConEU partners attend and try to engage with, although no formal synergy was formed yet.

⁷ <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/topic-details/ict-58-2020>

⁸ <https://africaeurope-innovationpartnership.net/>

Table 2 - AfriConEU's synergies with other networks, projects and initiatives

Name	Website	Type	Brief description of the involvement
DIGILOGIC	https://digilogic.africa/	Project	ICT-58 Family meetings.
HUBiquitous	https://hubiquitous.eu/	Project	ICT-58 Family meetings.
AEDIB NET	https://aedibnet.eu/	Project	ICT-58 Family meetings.
D4DHub	https://d4dhub.eu/	Project	ICT-58 Family meetings and participation in a meeting organised by the project.
Africa Europe Innovation Partnership	https://africaeurope-innovationpartnership.net/	Project	AfriConEU participated in 2 events of the Africa Europe Innovation Partnership project.

2.2.4. Talent Matchmaking

As stated previously, in addition to the KPIs presented for the Community of Practice, AfriConEU aims at contributing to “talent matchmaking”. Therefore, the Community Monitoring File includes a sheet to monitor the progress towards the achievement of this objective.

AfriConEU partners have been populating the *Job and Training Offers* sheet every week, having, at this moment, more than 100 entries that were already disseminated through the AfriConEU website and social media channels, or are up to consideration. Concretely, the AfriConEU communication and dissemination team has uploaded until the moment:

- **78 Job Opportunities on the website** (available on page <https://www.africoneu.eu/job-opportunities/>).
- **23 Job Opportunities on LinkedIn** (with a weekly post on Thursdays promoting job offers).

Moreover, and related to the forms mentioned in section 1.2.3., until now the Entity form received 2 responses and the Individuals form received 4 responses. To fight this low engagement, some promotional posts for this feature in the website are being designed and scheduled in order to promote a better matchmaking between the 2 main target groups of the project.

3. Next Steps

The community of practice results from the first year of the project (more concretely, 7 months since its launch on M6) are very positive and show a very good perspective for its future development. Nevertheless, joint efforts will have to be constantly made to update and adapt the current engagement strategies in place towards the achievement of the ambitious KPIs set for the end of the project.

Risk assessments and critical analyses on the methodology and results will be more explored by the AfriConEU partners, to identify weaknesses of the current strategy and understand how the project can increase its added value for the community and, thus, attract more stakeholders to the AfriConEU Community.

Lastly, as the community grows, the goal will be to encourage all the AfriConEU members to act as “ambassadors” of the project’s outcomes enforcing thus their sustainable uptake, even after the end of the project.

This report will be updated by M35, with the final Key Performance Indicators on interaction and value created within the AfriConEU Community of Practice.

Annex I – AfriConEU Community of Practice Form for Individuals

AfriConEU Community of Practice | Individuals

Do you want to be part of the AfriConEU Online Community of Practice and have access to various opportunities for training and funding? Then make sure you complete this form and stay updated!

The AfriConEU project essentially strengthens and reinforces the digital innovation ecosystems in Africa by targeting existing Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs) and supporting them through capacity building and networking activities. African DIHs are playing a central role in the development of digital entrepreneurship. By raising their capacities to tackle the challenges, they will be more effective in driving digital innovation forward.

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Status *

- Entrepreneur
- Stakeholder / Policymaker
- Investor
- Other

I am interested for... *

- Training Seminars
- Online Courses
- Webinars
- Funding
- Job Openings
- Conference
- Other

Annex II – AfriConEU Community of Practice Form for Entities

AfriConEU Community of Practice | Entities

Do you have an opportunity to offer to the AfriConEU Online Community? Are you looking to fill your Job Openings? Do you have exciting Training Seminars and are looking for participants? Then make sure to share all the required information with us, and we will spread the word around the AfriConEU Online Community of Practice!

The AfriConEU project essentially strengthens and reinforces the digital innovation ecosystems in Africa by targeting existing Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs) and supporting them through capacity building and networking activities. African DIHs are playing a central role in the development of digital entrepreneurship. By raising their capacities to tackle the challenges, they will be more effective in driving digital innovation forward.

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Type of Opportunity *

- Training Seminars
- Online Courses
- Webinars
- Funding
- Job Openings
- Conference
- Other

Title of Opportunity *

Thematic area *

Short Description *

Is there a deadline to apply? *

- Yes
- No

If yes, when?

mm/dd/yyyy

Link for more information *

Contact e-mail *

Annex III - The AfriconEU Monitoring Register File

GUIDE :
HOW TO FILL IN THE ENGAGEMENT MONITORING FILE OF THE AFRICONEU COMMUNITY OF PRACTICE

AfriConEU aims to create a vibrant and active Community of Practice between DIHs and innovation stakeholders from both Europe and Africa. The community will be stimulated to form the exchange of knowledge, experiences and connect different stakeholders.

Through this community, AfriConEU aims to attain some ambitious KPI's:

Number of stakeholders reached through the Online AfricanEU Community	>3000
Connections made for exchange of knowledge through the AfriConEU online community	>200
Number of synergies with relevant trans-continental and inter-continental networks, projects and initiatives	>40

In order to track and collect all relevant information to not only understand the community value to the DIHs but also to monitoring the KPI's of the respective project task (T5.1), this file was developed to be a living document, always up to date.

GUIDELINES	
Sheet	Main Purpose
Stakeholders	List of stakeholders involved in the AfriConEU Community of Practice
Connections	List of connections made for exchange of knowledge through the AfriConEU Community of Practice
Synergies	List of synergies with relevant trans-continental and inter-continental networks, projects and initiatives
Talent Matchmaking	List of disseminated job offers via the AfriConEU Community of Practice

WHAT INFORMATION DOES EACH SHEET CONTAIN AND HOW CAN I USE IT?

STAKEHOLDERS		
Lists all stakeholders reached through the AfriConEU Community of Practice.		
All stakeholders involved in AfriConEU events/activities (roundtables, interviews, events, bootcamps, etc.) and in the online community should be listed in this sheet (along with their respective information). Each partner is responsible to fill in the document with information concerning their leading activities/events.		
GENERAL RULES	Event / Activity	Indicate the event or activity in which the person concerned took part.
	Type of Involvement	Attendee / Speaker / Moderator / Interviewee / Etc.
	Type of Organisation	Please indicate to which type of organisation the stakeholder belongs to: start-up, DIHUB, investor, accelerator, entrepreneur, etc.
	Country	If not possible to indicate the country, name the continent.
	AfriConEU Partner	Please identify which AfriConEU partner is filling in the respective information.
CONNECTIONS		
List of connections made for the exchange of knowledge through the AfriConEU Community of Practice.		
All stakeholders involved in AfriConEU events/activities (roundtables, interviews, events, bootcamps, etc.) that are related to exchange of knowledge should be listed in this sheet (along with their respective information). Each partner is responsible to fill in the document with information concerning their leading activities/events.		
GENERAL RULES	Event / Activity	Indicate the event or activity in which the person concerned took part.
	Type of Involvement	Attendee / Speaker / Moderator / Interviewee / Etc.
	Type of Organisation	Please indicate to which type of organisation the stakeholder belongs to: start-up, DIHUB, investor, accelerator, entrepreneur, etc.
	Country	If not possible to indicate the country, name the continent.
	AfriConEU Partner	Please identify which AfriConEU partner is filling in the respective information.
SYNERGIES		
Lists the synergies created with relevant trans-continental and inter-continental networks, projects and initiatives.		
Project Partners should add to this list all the projects, initiatives or networks that are connected to AfriConEU in some way.		
GENERAL RULES	Type of Organisation	Please indicate the type of organisation: start-up, DIHUB, investor, accelerator, entrepreneur, etc.
	Person of Contact	Please provide the contact details of the person with whom we have direct contact.
	AfriConEU Partner	Please identify which AfriConEU partner is filling in the respective information.
TALENT MATCHMAKING		
Lists all the job and training offers disseminated via the AfriConEU's channels.		
YMH is the prime responsible to keep this section up to date however if any other partner is aware of some job offer that can or was disseminated among the AfriConEU's community should also fill in this sheet.		
GENERAL RULES	Promotor of the job / training offer	Provide information on the entity that requested the dissemination of the job offer.
	Dissemination channel(s)	Please indicate in which channels did we disseminate the respective job offer: Website, LinkedIn, Facebook, Newsletter, etc.
	Type of Offer	Please indicate if the offer to disseminate is a job offer or a training offer
	AfriConEU Partner	Please identify which AfriConEU partner is filling in the respective information.
	Deadline to apply	Please indicate which is the deadline to submit or apply to the job offer / training.

IS THERE ANY INFORMATION MISSING?

This document is constantly being updated!

If you notice that any information is missing, or if you have suggestions to make it better / more intuitive, please do not hesitate to contact us:

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ana.aleixo@inova.business
marta.coto@inova.business
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Number of stakeholders reached through the AfriconEu Community of Practice

Please, before entering any information, confirm if the person involved in your event/activity has already been added to the list. If so, please write and specify the situation in the column *Other comments / remarks*.

Event / Activity	Type of Involvement	Name	Gender	E-mail	Phone Number	Organisation	Website	Type of Organisation	Position	Country	AfriConEU Partner	Other comments / remarks
1												
2												
3												
4												
5												
6												
7												
8												
9												
10												
11												
12												
...												

Total

Connections made for exchange of knowledge through the AfriconEu Community of Practice

Please, before entering any information, confirm if the person involved in your event/activity has already been added to the list. If so, please write and specify the situation in the column *Other comments / remarks*.

Event / Activity	Type of Involvement	Name	Gender	E-mail	Phone Number	Organisation	Website	Type of Organisation	Position	Country	AfriConEU Partner	Other comments / remarks
1												
2												
3												
4												
5												
6												
7												
8												
9												
10												
11												
12												
...												

Total

Number of synergies with relevant trans-continental and inter-continental networks, projects and initiatives

	Name	Website	Type	Person of Contact		Brief description of the involvement	AfriConEU Partner	Participation in AfriConEU events/activities?
				Name	Email			
1								
2								
3								
4								
5								
6								
7								
8								
9								
10								
11								
12								
13								
14								
15								
16								
...								

Total

TALENT MATCHMAKING										
JOBS AND TRAINING OFFERS										
Promotor of the job / training offer				Brief description of the offer	Type of Offer	AfriConEU Partner	Dissemination channel(s)	Link(s) to the job offer	Deadline to apply	Other comments / remarks
Organisation Name	Type of Organisation	Name of Person of Contact	Email of Person of Contact							
1										
2										
3										
4										
5										
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